

TYPES OF WINTER WHEAT

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Abstract: his article provides information about wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.), including its types, particularly hard and soft wheat varieties.

Keywords: Soft wheat, common wheat, hard wheat, soft and hard wheat varieties.

Types of Wheat Wheat belongs to the genus *Triticum*. The most widespread and economically important species are soft wheat and hard wheat. These two species differ mainly in the protein content of their grains. Hard wheat flour is primarily used for pasta production. In Uzbekistan, hard wheat is less common than soft wheat. These species also differ significantly in their morphological characteristics. Soft Wheat or Common Wheat (*Triticum aestivum*) The spike is long and loose, with a relatively broad front side. It may be either awned or awnless. The awns are usually shorter than the spike and spread outward in a fan-like shape. The grain has a tuft at its tip. Its surface is floury or semi-vitreous. Soft wheat includes both spring and winter forms. Soft wheat flour is highly valued and widely used in the baking industry due to its excellent bread-making qualities.

Hard Wheat (*Triticum durum*) Hard wheat ranks second in terms of cultivated area. Its spike is large, and the grains are densely arranged. Only awned forms exist. The awns are long, thick, and oriented parallel to the spike. The grains are large, elongated, and taper downward. In cross-section, the grain is angular, whereas soft wheat grains are generally round. The grain surface is vitreous and glossy. The tuft at the grain tip is either very small or absent. Hard wheat flour is mainly used for producing high-quality pasta, vermicelli, and wheat groats. Compared to soft wheat flour, it produces bread of lower quality with less porous texture. Hard wheat is mainly cultivated as a spring crop. Classification of Wheat Based on morphological and economic characteristics, all cultivated wheat species are divided into two groups:

1. True or Naked Wheat True wheat has a strong rachis, and when the spike matures, it does not break into separate spikelets. The grain is naked and can be easily threshed. This group includes ten species, such as hard wheat, Mesopotamian wheat, Polonicum, Turgidum, round-grained wheat, soft wheat, Van wheat, and several others.
2. Spelt-like or Hulled Wheat Spelt-like wheat differs in that its spike rachis is brittle and breaks into separate spikelets when mature. During threshing, the grain remains enclosed within the glumes and does not separate easily. This group includes the

remaining fourteen wheat species, such as wild einkorn wheat, cultivated einkorn wheat, spelt wheat, zanduri wheat, emmer wheat, and others.

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